

around 27.00, 15.50 and 9.50 kK corresponding to three octahedral transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). There is a very strong charge transfer absorption around 39.00–41.00 kK which obscures the ν_3 transition. Both the ν_2 and ν_1 bands show pronounced splitting with two distinct components, confirming the pseudo-octahedral structures with approximate D_4h symmetry⁷. In the spectra of the Co^{II} complexes, bands centered around 9.00, 15.00 and 22.50 kK are observed which are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions of distorted octahedral symmetry⁸. The spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes show bands at 15.50 and 33.50 kK assigned to be due to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions of octahedral symmetry⁹. In the spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes ν_3 , ν_2 and ν_1 bands are seen at 24.00, 15.00 and 11.00 kK corresponding to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6T_{1g}$ (4G), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ (4G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6T_{1g}$ (4P) transitions. Their position and weak intensity correspond to distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰.

The values of all the ligand field parameters have been calculated using standard equations (Table 2) which are also in agreement with the octahedral structures of the complexes. The large Dq values are probably an outcome of the stability conferred in the complexes due to the formation of polymeric structures while the B and β values show sufficient degree of covalent character on metal-ligand bond involving some pi-type interaction¹¹.

In order to get a relative idea of the thermal stability of these polymeric complexes, their thermooxidative degradation was studied by thermogravimetry. These data show that the heat resistance temperatures of these lie in the range 250–300°. The initial weight-loss ($8 \pm 2\%$) at $320 \pm 10^\circ$ corresponds to the coordinated water in the complexes. The complexes exhibit reasonable stability upto 450°, as these do not melt but slowly darken to black powder after 24 h.

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Outersphere Association of Cobalt(III) Complexes: α, α' -Dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-Phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) Salts

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NUMEROUS data have been published on outersphere association of cobalt(III) complexes. But there are hardly any literature data for the composition and stability of outersphere cobalt(III) complexes other than hexamine¹⁻⁵, tris-ethylenediamine^{1,2,6,7}, acidopentamine⁸ and acidotetramine^{9,10} cobalt(III) complexes. This investigation is undertaken to fill partly the above gap in the chemistry of cobalt(III) outersphere complexes. In continuation of our previous study¹¹ we report herein the conductance behaviour of α, α' -dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate salts in dilute aqueous solution at 25° in terms of Onsager's theory and also determine their outersphere association constant. The association constants were found to increase in the order: $\text{SO}_4^{2-} \gg \text{Cl}^- \gg \text{Br}^- \gg \text{I}^-$. However Pyartman *et al.*¹² studied the following system: (i) $[\text{Rh}(\text{phen})_3] \text{L}_3^{3-n}$ ($\text{L} = \text{I}^-, \text{Br}^-$), (ii) $[\text{Rh}(\text{DMF})_6]^{3+} \text{L}^-$ ($\text{L} = \text{HCOO}^-, \text{OAc}^-, \text{EtCOO}^-, \text{PrCOO}^-$) and (iii) $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2]^{3+} \text{L}^-$ ($\text{L} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{ClO}_4^-$), where they obtained the result opposite to that predicted from electrostatic theories of ion association. They explained these results by considering the hydrophobic properties of cationic complexes.

Experimental

α, α' -Dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) chloride were

prepared by the reported method^{1,2}. The bromide, iodide and sulphate salts were prepared by metathetic reaction on the chloride salts. These samples were purified by recrystallisation from conductivity water. The purity of the sample was examined by chemical analysis and spectral measurements. The stock solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the sample in double-distilled water of low specific conductance.

The conductance of all the solutions in water was measured using a Leeds and Northrup conductance bridge. A Phillips conductivity cell was used. The conductivity cell was held in a water-bath maintained at 25±0.1°. The cell constant (0.775 cm⁻¹) was determined in the usual way with standard aqueous potassium chloride solution of known specific conductivity. In these experiments a frequency of 1000c/s was maintained and the solution was shaken vigorously before the measurement of conductance. Solvent correction was applied to each conductivity data.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constant of outersphere complex,

$[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\text{Cl}^- \rightleftharpoons [\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+} + \text{Cl}^-$
is calculated as follows. Let m =molar concentration of the salt, α =degree of dissociation of the ion pair $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\text{Cl}^-$, αm =concentration of $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$ ion, $(1-\alpha)m$ =concentration of the ion-pair.

Ionic strength,

$$I = 1/2\{[\text{Cl}^-] + 4[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\text{Cl}^- + 9[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\}$$

$$= 1/2\{2(1-\alpha)m + 3\alpha m + 4(1-\alpha)m + 9\alpha m\}$$

$$= 3(1+\alpha)m = (1+\alpha)C \quad (1)$$

where C is concentration in equivalents per litre. The dissociation constant is given by

$$K = \frac{[\text{Cl}^-][\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}}{[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\text{Cl}^-}$$

$$= \frac{(2+\alpha)\alpha m f_1 f_2}{(1-\alpha) f_2}$$

where f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are the activity coefficients of Cl^- , $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}\text{Cl}^-$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$ ions respectively and are calculated from Debye-Hückel relation $\log f_i = -0.509 Z_i^2 I^{1/2}$, where f_i refers to the activity coefficients of Z_i ions.

Now the experimental solutions are treated as the mixture of (A) 3 : 1 valent salt of molar concentration αm and (B) 2 : 1 valent salt of molar concentration $(1-\alpha)m$, where α is the degree of dissociation of the ion-pair.

Onsager's conductivity equation^{1,4} at 25° for 3 : 1 valent salt,

$$\lambda_{3:1} = \lambda_{(3:1)\text{Onsager}}^0 - [0.7852 | Z_1 Z_2 | \frac{q \times \lambda_{(3:1)\text{Onsager}}^0}{1+q^{1/2}} + 30.32 | Z_1 + Z_2 |] I^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

and for 2 : 1 valent salt,

$$\lambda_{2:1} = \lambda_{(2:1)\text{Onsager}}^0 - [0.7852 | Z_1 Z_2 | \frac{q \times \lambda_{(2:1)\text{Onsager}}^0}{1+q^{1/2}} + 30.32 | Z_1 + Z_2 |] I^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$\lambda_{(3:1)\text{Onsager}}^0$ is obtained as follows. The theoretical slope b of Onsager's conductivity curve is determined from the plot of λ_{exp} vs $C^{1/2}$. Then $\lambda_{\text{exp}} + bC^{1/2}$ are plotted against C and extrapolated to zero concentration (Fig. 1). $\lambda_{(2:1)\text{Onsager}}^0$ is obtained from the relation^{1,5},

$$\frac{\lambda_{(2:1)\text{Onsager}}^0}{\lambda[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}} = \frac{|Z|}{3}$$

Fig. 1. Onsager extrapolation. $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]X_2$: (a) $X = \text{Cl}^-$, (b) $X = \text{Br}^-$, (c) $X = \text{I}^-$; $[\text{Co}(o\text{-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]X_2$: (d) $X = \text{Cl}^-$, (e) $X = \text{Br}^-$, (f) $X = \text{I}^-$.

where Z is the charge of the ion-pair, namely +2. The solvent corrected specific conductivity of the solution is given by

$$10^8 k = 3\alpha m \lambda_{[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}} + 2(1-\alpha)m \lambda_{[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2\text{Cl}]^{2+}} + \{3\alpha m + 2(1-\alpha)m\} \lambda_{\text{Cl}^-}$$

$$= 3\alpha m \lambda_{3:1} + 2(1-\alpha)m \lambda_{2:1}$$

Equivalent conductivity is given by

$$\lambda_{\text{exp}} = \frac{10^8 k}{3m} = \alpha \lambda_{3:1} + \frac{2}{3} (1-\alpha) \lambda_{2:1}$$

The equivalent conductivity in terms of ionic strength and degree of dissociation of the ion-pair at 25° of different salts are given below. From these relations and equation (1), α and I values are calculated by constant approximation methods. The dissociation constants thus obtained are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Conductivity equations at 25° are as follows.

For $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$,
 $\lambda = 79.18 - 91.46 I^{1/2} + \alpha(60.82 - 103.81 I^{1/2})$

For $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Br}_2$,
 $\lambda = 80.31 - 91.78 I^{1/2} + \alpha(61.19 - 103.78 I^{1/2})$

For [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]I₂,
 $\lambda = 79.50 - 91.56 I^{1/2} + \alpha(61.0 - 103.88 I^{1/2})$

For [Co(o-phen)(BigH)₂]Cl₂,
 $\lambda = 76.52 - 90.11 I^{1/2} + \alpha(57.48 - 100.68 I^{1/2})$

For [Co(o-phen)(BigH)₂]Br₂,
 $\lambda = 77.77 - 90.49 I^{1/2} + \alpha(58.02 - 100.82 I^{1/2})$

For [Co(o-phen)(BigH)₂]I₂,
 $\lambda = 76.62 - 90.10 I^{1/2} + \alpha(57.37 - 100.50 I^{1/2})$

In case of sulphate salts $\lambda_{\text{observed}}$, the equivalent conductance at zero concentration is obtained by summation of mean limiting conductivity of cation (obtained from chloride, bromide and iodide salt) and 80.0 at 25° for the ionic conductance of sulphate ion. The dissociation constant of the equilibrium :

where m is the molar concentration of the salt and x is the concentration of the ion-pair. The relation

between the observed conductivity and calculated conductivity is given by¹⁵

$$\lambda'_1 + \lambda''_1 - \lambda_{\text{exp}} = (x/c)(3\lambda'_1 + 2\lambda''_1 + \lambda'''_1)$$

where λ'_1 , λ''_1 and λ'''_1 are the ionic conductance of tri-, di-, and monovalent (ion-pair) ion in the 3:2 valent system. From the relation (3) and ionic strength equation $I = (2.5c - 6x)$ by approximating until constant x and I , the values of dissociation constant K has been calculated and are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Ionic conductivity equations 25° are as follows.

(i) For the system [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]₂(SO₄)₃,
 $[\text{Co(dipy)(BigH)}_2]^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-} \quad \lambda'_1 = 63.48 - 174.13 I^{1/2}$
 $[\text{Co(dipy)(BigH)}_2]^{+1} \cdot \text{SO}_4 \quad \lambda''_1 = 80.00 - 165.47 I^{1/2}$
 $\lambda'''_1 = 21.16 - 58.04 I^{1/2}$

(ii) For the system [Co(o-phen)(BigH)₂]₂(SO₄)₃,
 $[\text{Co(o-phen)(BigH)}_2]^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-} \quad \lambda'_1 = 57.40 - 165.60 I^{1/2}$
 $[\text{Co(o-phen)(BigH)}_2]^{+1} \cdot \text{SO}_4 \quad \lambda''_1 = 80.00 - 164.46 I^{1/2}$
 $\lambda'''_1 = 19.13 - 55.20 I^{1/2}$

TABLE 1—CONDUCTIVITY OF CoIII-DIPYRIDYL-BIS(BIGUANIDE) HALIDES AT 25°

$\times 10^4 C$	$\times 10^3 C^{1/2}$	λ_{exp}	$\lambda_{\text{exp}} + bc^{1/2}$	α	$\times 10^3 K$	Mean K	Mean association constant
Chloride salt :							
15.20	3.898	127.55	138.3	0.967 9	30.87		$K_A = 1/K$
13.37	3.656	128.60	138.7	0.975 4	36.63		
12.16	3.487	128.88	138.5	0.972 0	29.64		
10.94	3.307	129.70	138.8	0.978 2	35.13	0.036 8	27 0
9.73	3.119	130.40	139.0	0.981 7	38.10		
8.51	2.917	130.90	138.9	0.980 8	32.35		
7.29	2.700	131.80	139.2	0.986 4	40.26		
6.08	2.465	132.60	139.4	0.989 4	44.30		
Bromide salt :							
15.70	3.962	129.26	140.2	0.975 6	42.07		$K_A = 1/K$
14.60	3.821	129.74	140.3	0.977 4	42.93		
13.62	3.685	130.12	140.3	0.977 9	41.52		
12.52	3.535	130.63	140.4	0.979 7	42.25	0.049 4	23.0
11.39	3.349	131.14	140.4	0.980 9	41.61		
10.30	3.209	131.66	140.53	0.982 2	41.12		
9.40	3.066	132.25	140.72	0.985 8	47.92		
8.65	2.941	132.57	140.70	0.985 4	43.42		
Iodide salt :							
15.20	3.898	128.8	139.6	0.982 4	57.32		$K_A = 1/K$
13.37	3.656	129.4	139.5	0.981 3	48.55		
12.16	3.487	130.6	140.2	0.995 0	70.86	0.060 3	16.6
10.96	3.307	130.6	139.7	0.985 9	54.84		
9.73	3.119	131.3	139.9	0.989 3	66.49		
8.51	2.912	131.9	139.9	0.990 3	64.15		
7.29	2.700	132.6	140.0	0.992 1	69.88		
6.08	2.465	133.2	140.0	0.991 3	54.08		
Sulphate salt :							
$10^4 C$	$10^3 C^{1/2}$	λ_{emp}	$\times 10^3 z$	$\times 10^4 K$	Mean K	Mean association constant	$K_A = 1/K$
15.20	3.898	101.4	10.89	10.81			
13.39	3.656	102.8	9.42	10.22			
12.16	3.487	104.68	8.09	10.37	1×10^{-3}	10×10^3	
10.94	3.307	105.98	7.07	10.08			
9.72	3.119	107.99	5.90	10.12			
8.51	2.917	110.18	4.78	10.15			
7.29	2.700	117.7	3.97	9.50			
6.08	2.465	113.83	3.10	9.04			

NOTES

TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY OF Co^{III}-O-PHENANTHROLINE-BIS(BIGUANIDE) HALIDES AT 25°

$\times 10^4 C$	$\times 10^2 C^{1/2}$	λ_{exp}	$\lambda_{exp} + bc^{1/2}$	κ	$\times 10^4 K$	Mean K	Mean association constant		
Chloride salt :									
14.50	3.807	122.2	132.5	0.969 2	31.02	0.039 0	$K_A = 1/K$ 25.6		
13.34	3.652	122.8	132.6	0.974 0	34.52				
12.17	3.488	123.2	132.6	0.972 3	32.20				
11.02	3.319	123.8	132.7	0.975 4	31.20				
9.85	3.138	124.5	132.9	0.979 7	58.10				
8.698	2.949	125.2	133.1	0.988 6	38.66				
7.597	2.745	125.7	133.1	0.982 7	32.53				
6.368	2.523	126.5	133.3	0.986 7	24.14				
Bromide salt :									
15.08	3.883	124.3	134.8	0.980 0	50.18			0.050 0	$K_A = 1/K$ 20.0
13.88	3.725	124.9	134.9	0.983 6	57.50				
12.67	3.559	125.2	134.8	0.980 8	45.21				
11.47	3.386	125.8	134.9	0.983 5	48.77				
10.25	3.201	126.3	134.9	0.988 6	44.86				
7.839	2.745	127.6	135.1	0.988 0	48.70				
6.634	2.575	128.3	135.2	0.989 9	50.19				
5.428	2.329	129.1	135.4	0.992 5	56.84				
Iodide salt :									
14.69	3.832	123.1	133.4	0.988 5	85.67	0.079 3	$K_A = 1/K$ 12.6		
12.92	3.594	123.8	133.5	0.989 7	86.95				
11.75	3.427	124.2	133.4	0.988 8	73.82				
10.58	3.252	125.0	133.7	0.995 4	165.00				
9.399	3.065	125.3	133.5	0.991 4	79.69				
8.224	2.867	126.0	133.7	0.994 7	116.50				
6.985	2.643	126.6	133.7	0.994 7	100.20				
5.875	2.424	127.0	133.5	0.991 1	51.10				
4.700	2.168	127.8	133.6	0.993 3	55.60				
Sulphate salt									
$\times 10^4$	$\times 10^2 C^{1/2}$	λ_{exp}	$\times 10^5 z$	$10^4 K$	Mean K	Mean association constant			
15.20	3.898	98.83	10.03	12.07	0.001 2	$K_A = 1/K$ 8×10^3			
13.37	3.656	100.80	8.35	12.00					
12.16	3.487	102.40	7.05	12.42					
10.94	3.307	103.80	6.22	11.90					
9.728	3.119	105.60	5.19	11.93					
8.512	2.917	107.60	4.14	12.23					
7.296	2.700	109.90	3.27	12.13					
6.080	2.465	112.80	2.35	12.66					

According to Fuoss equation¹⁶, the ion association constant is given by

$$K_A = \frac{4\pi N}{3000} a^2 e^b$$

where $b = Z_+ Z_- e_0^2 / D a k T$, and a is a distance of closest approach, e_0 the charge of the electron, k the Boltzmann constant, D the dielectric constant of the medium, Z_+, Z_- are the charges of the interacting ions. From this expression it is expected that smaller the size and higher the charge, greater will be the formation constant of the outersphere complex. Considering the charge and size of the anions we may expect the increasing order of stability as: iodide < bromide < chloride << sulphate. Both the systems have outersphere association constants of the expected order and comparable to those of the ion pairs reported in the literature. Results in Table 3 suggests that an increase of the charge and decrease of the dimension of the outersphere ligands as well as complex ions result in an

increase of the stability of the outersphere complex which is in accordance with the suggestion of Fuoss. The observed values of the association constants are comparable but smaller than the values reported in the literature (Table 4) for the

TABLE 3—VALUES OF MEAN ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR 1 : 1 OUTERSPHERE ASSOCIATION OF COBALT(III) HALIDE/SULPHATE AT 25°

Complex-halide/sulphate	Mean association constant
Cobalt(III)-bis(biguanide)(dipyridyl)	
-chloride	27.0
-bromide	23.0
-iodide	16.6
-sulphate	10×10^3
Cobalt(III)-bis(biguanide)(orthophenanthroline)	
-chloride	25.6
-bromide	20.0
-iodide	12.6
-sulphate	8×10^3

halide and the sulphate ion-pairs of complexed cobalt(III).

TABLE 4—log ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (log β) AT 25°

[Co(NH ₃) ₆] ³⁺ .Z ⁻		[Co(en) ₃] ³⁺ .Z ⁻	
Z ⁻	log β	Z ⁻	log β
Cl ⁻	1.48 ^a	Cl ⁻	1.72 ^a
	1.87 ^b		0.99 ^c
	0.96 ^c		
Br ⁻	1.50 ^d	Br ⁻	1.32 ^b
	1.66 ^b		
	0.96 ^c		
I ⁻	1.77 ^e	SO ₄ ²⁻	3.10 ^c
	1.77 ^f		2.98 ^g
	-0.40 ^h		
SO ₄ ²⁻	3.56 ^a		
	3.26 ^c		
	3.50 ^b		

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 17. ^fRef. 18. ^gRef. 19. ^hRef. 20. ⁱRef. 7.

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Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Chloride catalysed Oxidation of Glycollic Acid and Ethanol by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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RUTHENIUM compounds are very important from the technological point of view¹. Oxidation of diols in alkaline solution by sodium hypochlorite using ruthenium(III) chloride catalyst gives extensive carbon bond cleavage². Oxidation of glycols³ and cycloalcohols⁴ has been reported from our laboratory. In the present study oxidation of glycollic acid and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) using ruthenium(III) chloride as a homogeneous catalyst has been undertaken to see how the change in the reactive group in organic substrate, keeping the number of carbon atoms same, effects the reaction kinetics and whether ruthenium(III) chloride catalyses the oxidation of organic compounds having different reactive groups by hydride ion transfer only or the charge transfer process is also there.

Experimental

Glycollic acid (Riedel) and ethanol (B.D.H.) were used as such. Hexacyanoferrate(III) (AnalaR) was dissolved in the double-distilled water. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the final strengths of the acid and the catalyst were 3.342×10^{-3} and 2.74×10^{-2} M respectively. All other chemicals used were either AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

The progress of the reaction was measured at different intervals of time by estimating the hexacyanoferrate(II) produced by titrating it against a standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as a redox indicator. Temperature of the reaction was kept constant by keeping the reaction mixture into an electrically operated thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of glycollic acid and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was studied under the conditions where the uncatalysed reaction was negligible. Ionic strength of the medium was kept constant with the help of a standard solution of potassium chloride although the change in the ionic strength of the medium does not affect the reaction velocity. In the kinetic measurements rate of the reaction is given in terms of the dc/dt values obtained from the initial slopes of the zero order plots and are shown in the terms of remaining hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations per minute.